

Additional file 8. Expression of lignin and xylan biosynthetic genes

	<i>F5H</i>	<i>COMT</i>	<i>GT43A</i>	<i>GT43B</i>
WT	1.05 ± 0.22	1.06 ± 0.25	1.04 ± 0.19	1.06 ± 0.23
4	0.71 ± 0.16	0.86 ± 0.16	1.08 ± 0.16	1.33 ± 0.06
8	1.00 ± 0.14	0.84 ± 0.02	0.81 ± 0.13	0.83 ± 0.21
17	1.82 ± 0.72	1.58 ± 0.49	1.3 ± 0.12	1.49 ± 0.35

Transcript level of different genes in developing wood determined by RT-qPCR. Actin, ubiquitin and cytochrome P450 were used as reference genes and expression levels were normalized to WT.

Means ± *SE*, *n* = 3 biological replicates.